

Variation in Locus of Control among Technical and Non-technical College Students: Evidence from Higher Education Institutions in Bihar

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Locus of control has been linked to academic achievement and a person's overall success in life. Although many Indian and international studies have associated Locus of control with motivation, educational competencies, mental health, and adjustment, relatively few empirical studies have explicitly focused on stream-wise differences in the context of higher education in Bihar. The Primary objective of this study is to identify differences in the locus of control among students from both technical and non-technical colleges and to draw meaningful conclusions based on research evidence. This study is based on the larger doctoral thesis. The sample consists of 309 undergraduate students (155 males, 154 females) from both technical ($n=157$) and non-technical ($n=152$) colleges situated in Bihar. Data was collected through the Locus of Control Scale (Adult) by Singh and Bhardwaj (2010) a standardised Indian instrument available in Hindi/English. Descriptive and inferential statistics, including chi-square tests, ANOVA, and regression analysis, were used to draw inferences from the collected data. The Type of college was a significant predictor, indicating that students from different college types scored differently on locus of control. However, gender was not a significant predictor, suggesting no meaningful gender-based difference in locus of control in this sample. Locus of control is an important part of the personality spectrum. It has an observable connection to academic achievement. It also impacts the mental and physical well-being of students. Educational institutions need to actively address such demanding personality traits among students.

Keywords: Internal-external locus of control, Bihar, higher education, inferential statistics, engineering

Over the past decade, Bihar has seen a rapid expansion in the number of higher education institutions and the number of students enrolled in them. This phenomenon, in addition to the lack of employability country-wide and other factors, has exposed these young adults to intense academic competition, uncertainty and psychosocial stress. In this context, locus of control has become a key personality variable that forms students' concept of success and failure, as well as how they will engage with academic tasks.

Locus of control (LOC) is an important personality attribute that plays a vital role in shaping young adults' motivational and cognitive-behavioural patterns. It is a psychological construct that describes how individuals attribute control over events and

outcomes in their lives. Psychologist Julian B. Rotter first introduced the concept of locus of control as a key construct within his social learning theory. He defined it as "*Internal vs. external control refers to the degree to which persons expect that a reinforcement or an outcome of their behaviour is contingent on their own behaviour or personal characteristic vs. the degree to which persons expect that the reinforcement or outcome is a function of chance, luck, or fate, is under the control of powerful others or is simply unpredictable. Such expectancies may generalise along a gradient based on the degree of semantic similarity of the situational cues*" (Rotter, 1966).

A person with an internal locus believes that their life outcomes are determined by their own actions. In contrast, a person with an external locus of control believes that outcomes in their lives are determined by external forces such as fate, luck, the system, or other people's constructs (Rotter, 1990). Subsequent research across cultures has shown that LOC is indeed linked to academic performance and well-being (Rotter, 1966; Lopez-Garrido, 2023). A greater internal LOC is typically associated with greater conscientiousness, relentless effort, persistence and academic achievement, whereas a greater external LOC is linked with feelings of despair, helplessness and avoidance (Findley & Cooper, 1983; Youse, 2012). The locus of control shows notable differences among college students. Research indicates that gender, cultural and educational contexts also influence these differences.

Auliya et al. (2023) investigated the influence of internal LOC and academic self-efficacy on academic adjustment among college students. This study observed that internal LOC and academic

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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self-efficacy affect adjustment of college students, specially in academic settings. This study's other finding was that if we improve these two factors even by a minimal percentage, it would have a remarkable effect on students' success in education because it would make them empowered to handle the challenges of academic life. Many studies have indicated that an internal locus of control is connected to better achievement in the academic field. As it brings a reduction in behaviours that hamper goal-oriented actions (Kim, 2024; Gujjar & Aijaz, 2014). Students who have a strong internal LOC, feel responsible for learning. So they usually perform better in exams and other assessments. This leads to a successful life. Internal locus of control is generally beneficial but in some cases, students blame themselves too much that may cause stress and anxiety. Due to this, it is important to have a balance. Learning to set realistic expectations is also beneficial for students. Manichander (2012) observed in his study that internal LOC empowers student, they believe that it is their effort and capability which will determine success or failure. So, they become more capable to tackle hardships in academic life. Haidari et al. (2023) conducted a meta-analytic study of LOC, self-efficacy and motivation to student achievement and found that LOC directly impacts motivation. Most of the research evidence suggests that external LOC may negatively influence motivation and ultimately academic performance.

In India, many studies have found that internal LOC correlates positively with academic performance and adaptive psychological outcomes among students, whether in school or college. Yadav (2023) conducted a study of undergraduate humanities students at the University of Delhi and concluded that internal LOC was consistently associated with higher academic scores across 10th grade, 12th grade, and the early years of graduation. In Bihar, Rani and Sinha (2022) studied university students. They found that LOC is one of the key constructs influencing youth development, and those with more internal LOC reported higher life satisfaction and adjustment.

Existing research on locus-of-control differences by course type is limited and yields mixed findings. Some studies have reported no significant differences in locus of control between students of different academic majors. Naik (2015) conducted a survey of 171 college students in Gulbarga (Karnataka) and found no significant difference in LoC scores between science and arts students (course of study). Additionally, no link was found between locus of control and gender at the level of the locus of control. Similarly, Napowanetz (2014) conducted a study in the USA examining STEM majors versus non-STEM majors and found that academic major was not significantly associated with locus of control orientation, nor were there gender differences in LoC in that sample. Based on these studies, it appears that attending a technical or non-technical college alone does not determine LOC level. Many studies have noted a lack of extensive literature on this topic, indicating a need for further investigation into whether specific fields of study attract or produce students with differing control perceptions.

On the contrary, some studies found a connection between the course of study and the level of LOC. Suraj et al. (2024) studied Indian students studying for MBA. They tried to link educational background in graduation of these students with internal-external orientation. They found that students who have graduated in Engineering (B.Tech.), Arts (B.A.) and, Business Administration (BBA) scored higher on internal LOC than students who graduated in Science (B.Sc.) and other courses. In their sample, about 86% of

engineering and arts graduates were classified as having an internal LoC, versus roughly 53% for science graduates. This suggests that students coming from technical engineering and arts backgrounds were more likely to believe in personal control of outcomes than those from pure sciences.

Apart from academic orientation, gender is another factor often examined in studies of locus of control. Classic theories did not assert significant gender differences in LoC, but cultural factors might influence any gaps. For instance, a study on Pakistani college students (Zaidi & Mohsin, 2013) found that males showed significantly more internal locus of control, whereas females were more external on average. The authors attributed this to socialisation patterns in which males may be encouraged to be more independent and girls to be more protected, potentially affecting their perceived control.

Nevertheless, stream-wise comparative studies between technical and non-technical college students in Bihar are very few. Technical and non-technical students face a different academic environment, a different curriculum and a different career progression, which in turn shapes and mediates their perception of control. The landscape of higher education is ever evolving. It is essential to study its dynamics regularly. This study is an attempt to explore this vital gap in knowledge by comparing students from technical and non-technical colleges situated in Bihar.

Review of Literature

To give this study a perspective and right direction, a detailed literature review was carried out. Conclusions from this review are also associated with the discussion and implications sections.

Studies Related to the Locus of Control Linked to the Academic Stream

Technical college students tend to have a stronger internal locus of control, which has been linked to higher academic achievement, as students with an internal LOC are more likely to engage in effective learning strategies and show greater perseverance (Hasan & Khalid, 2014; Kirkpatrick et al., 2008). Non-technical college students tend to show more external LOC, which is connected to poor self-confidence, that leads to poor achievement in academic life. It also impacts their self-efficacy negatively (Kirkpatrick et al., 2008; Reynolds, 1976). Cultural factors also play a role in shaping and reshaping the LOC. Wang and Xin (2023) noticed in their study that Chinese college students have shown stable levels of both internal and external LOC over the past two decades, suggesting cultural stability in LOC perceptions. In contrast, research based in the Western context often reports shifts toward a more external LOC among students, possibly due to changing educational environments and societal expectations (Wu et al., 2025; Wang & Xin, 2023). Socio-economic background and family environment also influence LOC. Students from higher socio-economic backgrounds have a possibility to develop a more internal LOC due to better access to resources and support, while those from lower socio-economic backgrounds might develop a more external LOC due to perceived limitations (Wu et al., 2025).

Studies Related to the Locus of Control Linked to Gender

In many studies, it was noted that male students lean towards more internal LOC and female students lean towards more external LOC.

This phenomenon is translated into a pattern where male students believe that their efforts and abilities are the cause of their success, while their failure is due to external factors. This perception of personal control over outcome boosts their self-confidence (Fatemi & Hoseiniyan, 2016; Nizam & Zulkipli, 2024). Conversely, female students often have an external locus of control. That means there is a greater possibility that female students will blame external factors like luck, fate or the influence of others or the system for their success and failure. This lack of self-confidence impacts students' self-esteem negatively and they start seeking external validation from others (Fatemi & Hoseiniyan, 2016; Sherman et al., 1997). Perception of control is also affected by cultural context. In one study of a Mexican university, it was noticed that both male and female students displayed an external locus of control. Here, gender became unimportant factor. Still, there was some difference, for example, male students scored higher on some specific portion of the study, like fate and political power (Jurado García et al., 2017). In academic settings, students who are high achievers, tend to have an internal locus of control. This is true for both male and female students. While in overall scenario, female students show a higher internal academic locus of control than male students. It indicates that the connection between academic achievement and gender is complex (Hasan & Khalid, 2014). A person with an internal LOC generally portrays better goal-setting and decision-making abilities, resulting in better self-regulation. Male students who generally tend to show internal LOC. They are also likely to perform better in decision-making tasks (Sidola et al., 2020; Nizam & Zulkipli, 2024). Gender differences also manifest in the way one perceives control over uncontrollable life events and interpersonal relationships. In general, women feel they do not have much control over these things, which significantly impacts their social adaptation. They also differ in the strategies they adopt to manage stress in their lives (Sherman et al., 1997; Zea & Tyler, 1994).

Objectives of the Study

- To describe the overall level and distribution of locus of control among undergraduate students in selected higher education institutions in Bihar.
- To examine differences in LOC levels between engineering (technical) and general degree (non-technical) students, and differences in LOC based on gender
- To infer and discuss the educational implications of LOC variation for teaching, counselling and institutional practices in Bihar's colleges.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H01*: There will be no significant difference between male and female college students in terms of the locus of control.
- *H02*: There will be no significant difference in the locus of control between technical and non-technical college students.
- *H03*: There will be no significant interaction effect between male-female and technical-non-technical college students about locus of control.

Method

Participants

This study used non-probability convenience sampling. It also used quota sampling to rationalise the sample by gender and college type.

While choosing colleges to draw a sample from, geographic location was one of the deciding factors. Within the college, students were randomly selected. This study was conducted on a total sample of $N=309$ undergraduate students drawn from colleges in Bihar. Of which, 155 were male and 154 were female students, ensuring near equal gender representation. The total sample was divided into two subgroups: students enrolled in technical courses, such as engineering, and related technical/professional programs, and students enrolled in non-technical courses or general degree courses, such as arts, humanities, commerce, and pure sciences. Out of 309, 157 students were from technical courses, and 152 students were from non-technical colleges. Students were mainly in the age group of 18 to 23 years. Students with chronic mental and physical health issues were excluded from the study. The following tables summarise the participants of this study.

Table 1

College Type and Gender Wise Sample Distribution

Type of colleges	Male	Female	Total	% of sample
Technical college	80	77	157	50.80%
Non-technical college	75	77	152	49.20%
Total	155	154	309	100%

Table 2

Course Type and Gender Wise Sample Distribution

Name of the course	Male	Female	Total
Bachelor of Arts (B.A.)	25	26	51
Bachelor of commerce (B.COM.)	25	25	50
bachelor of science (B.Sc.)	25	26	51
Bachelor of Technology (Mechanical Engineering)	20	19	39
Bachelor of Technology (Electrical Engineering)	20	19	39
Bachelor of Technology (Civil Engineering)	20	18	38
Bachelor of Technology (Computer Science Engineering)	20	19	39

Research Design

This will be an empirical study. This cross-sectional survey study uses primary data from a larger doctoral thesis examining the psychological correlates of students from technical (engineering) and non-technical (general degree) colleges in Bihar. It uses a comparative quantitative approach.

Measure

Locus of control was measured using the Locus of Control scale (Adult) developed by Singh and Bhardwaj (2010). This scale is based on Nowicki and Strickland's (1973) LOC scale. This scale

is available in both Hindi and English and demonstrates high reliability and validity. The present study used the Hindi version of this test. Scoring on the locus of control scale ranges from 0 to 40. 0-8 is interpreted as a low score, indicating an internal locus of control. Most participants scored 9-16 marks, which is the average. Such students tend to have mixed LOC. Meaning they may have an internal LOC in some setups but an external LOC in others. 17-40 marks a high score; such a person tends to have an external locus of control, meaning they blame external factors such as fate and the system for their life outcomes.

Data Analysis

After administering the questionnaire, the raw data were converted to scores using the scoring key. The primary tool for data analysis was Microsoft Excel (2021) with occasional use of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 19. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were both used to draw meaningful conclusions from the data. A two-way ANOVA was used to analyse whether gender and type of college act independently or whether their combined effect differs from the sum of their individual effects. The Chi-square (X^2) Statistic was used to analyse whether there is an association between locus of control levels and gender and college type. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine the predictive value of gender and college type on locus of control scores.

Results

Descriptive Statistics of Locus of Control Scores

Table 3

Showing Mean, SD and Other Descriptive Statistics of LOC (N=309)

Variable	Min.	Max.	Mean (M)	SD	Skew.	Kurt.
Locus of Control	1	27	16.61	4.54	-0.095	-0.45

Table 3 shows a mean LOC score of 16.61 (SD 4.54), indicating a moderate level of perceived control and considerable variability among students. On average, participants scored slightly above the mid-range of the scale. This may indicate that the majority of respondents tend toward a moderate to slightly external locus of control, meaning they attribute outcomes to external forces such as luck, fate, or powerful others rather than solely to their own abilities or efforts. The frequency distribution shows a minimum score of 1, while the maximum score is 27. So the range of scores is 26. It can be inferred that sample response is wide and shows variation in respondent's orientation toward perception of control. In the scale used in this study, a lower score represents a higher internal locus of control and a higher score represents a higher external locus of control. The standard deviation (SD) of these scores is 4.54. It is proof that scores are moderately spread around the mean. This indicates that while there is some consistency in responses, participants differ meaningfully in how they perceive the control of events in their lives. The skewness value is negative but very close to zero, which means the distribution of scores is approximately symmetric. There is no substantial clustering toward either the high

(external) or low (internal) end. A skewness near zero suggests that participants are relatively evenly distributed across the spectrum of locus of control beliefs. The kurtosis value is slightly below zero, indicating a platykurtic distribution. This suggests the distribution is flatter than a standard normal distribution. There are more moderate scores and fewer extreme scores than expected in a normal distribution. The distribution is nearly normal, indicating the sample is suitable for parametric tests such as t-tests, ANOVA, or regression analysis.

Table 4

Level of Locus of Control-wise Distribution of the Sample, based on Gender

	Locus of Control		
	High	Average	Low
Male	75	74	6
Female	79	73	2
Total	154	147	8
Percentage	49.84	47.57	2.59

Table 4 shows that, out of 309 students, 154 (49.84%) have a high locus of control. 147 students fall into the average locus of control category, which constitutes 47.57%. Only eight students had a low locus of control, which is 2.59%. Out of the total 155 male students. Seventy-five of them were in the high locus of control category, 74 in the average category, and 6 in the low locus of control category. Of the total 154 female students, 79 were in the high category, 73 in the average category, and only 2 in the low LOC category.

Incidentally, 49.84% of students exhibit an external locus of control, meaning they believe external factors are responsible for their life outcomes. 47.57% of students attribute their life outcomes to both external and internal factors. Only a meagre 2.59% of students believe they are responsible for their life outcomes and choices.

Table 5

Level of Locus of Control-wise Sample Distribution based on the Type of College

	Locus of Control		
	High	Average	Low
Technical	68	86	03
Non-technical	86	61	05
Total	154	147	8
Percentage	49.84	47.57	2.59

Table 5 shows the segregation of scores between high, average and low according to the technical-non-technical sub-group of the sample. Of 157 technical students, 68 scored high, 86 scored average, and only three scored low. For non-technical students, 86 out of 152 students were in the high LOC Category, 61 in the average LOC category, and only 5 in the low LOC category.

Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics is used to draw conclusions from the data.

Data Analysis for Locus of Control with ANOVA

Table 6

Shows the 'F' value of the Different Groups in Relation to the Locus of Control

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p	F crit
Gender [A]	0.120	1.000	0.120	0.006	0.939	3.873
Type of College [B]	161.333	1.000	161.333	7.967	0.005	3.873
Interaction(A×B)	0.853	1.000	0.853	0.042	0.837	3.873
Within	5994.080	296.000	20.250			
Total	6156.387	299.000				

Ho1: There will be no significant difference between male and female college students in terms of the locus of control.

Table 7

Table Showing Mean, SD, F-Value, for Locus of Control

Gender	N	Mean	SD	F	p
Male	155	16.56	4.689	0.006	0.939
Female	154	16.66	4.409		

Table 7 suggests that the mean locus of control score for males ($M = 16.56$) and females ($M = 16.66$) is nearly identical. This suggests that both male and female participants demonstrate a similar level of locus of control orientation. The standard deviation is slightly higher for males ($SD = 4.689$) than for females ($SD = 4.409$). This means male responses show slightly more variability. Female scores are slightly more consistent. The F-value = 0.006 indicates a minimal variance between groups compared to within-group variance. The p-value = 0.939, indicating that the observed difference is not statistically significant. The null hypothesis is rejected. There is no meaningful difference in locus of control between male and female students in the sample. Both genders appear to share similar beliefs regarding whether internal efforts or external forces determine life outcomes.

Ho2: There will be no significant difference in the locus of control between technical and non-technical college students.

Table 8

Showing Mean, SD, F-Value, t-Value for Locus of Control

Type of College	N	Mean	SD	F	p
Technical	157	19.95	4.4	7.967	0.005
Non-technical	152	17.29	4.60		

Table 8 indicates that the mean score for technical college students ($M = 19.95$) is notably higher than that for non-technical college students ($M = 17.29$). Since higher scores on the locus of control

scale indicate a more external orientation, this suggests that Students in technical colleges tend to have a more external locus of control compared to students in non-technical colleges. The standard deviations are similar, indicating that both groups exhibit comparable variability in locus of control scores. Individual differences exist in both groups, but the distributions of scores are nearly equal. The F-value of 7.967 indicates a meaningful difference between groups. Furthermore, p-value = 0.005, which is less than 0.05, confirms that this difference is statistically significant. The null hypothesis is accepted. Technical college students demonstrate a more external locus of control, while students from non-technical colleges demonstrate a relatively more internal locus of control.

Ho3: There will be no significant interaction effect between male-female and technical-non-technical college students about locus of control.

Table 9

Table Showing the Mean and F-value for the Interaction Effect between the Male-female and Technical-non-technical Students in the Context of Locus of Control

Gender [A]	College type [B]	Mean	F	p
Male[A1]	Technical[B1]	15.79	0.042	0.837
	Non-technical[B2]	17.36		
Female[A2]	Technical[B1]	15.93		
	Non-technical[B2]	17.29		

Table 9 indicates that the two-way ANOVA revealed that the interaction effect between gender and type of college on locus of control was not statistically significant, $F(1, 305) = 0.042$, $p = .837$. Although non-technical college students scored higher on locus of control than technical students, this pattern was consistent across both genders. Therefore, gender does not moderate the relationship between college type and locus of control.

Data Analysis with Chi-Square

Table 10

Table Showing the Association between the Type of Colleges and Locus of Control

	Level of locus of control			Row Total	Chi-square value (X^2)	p
	High	Average	Low			
Technical	68	86	3	157	6.77	0.034
Non-technical	86	61	5	152		
Column Total	154	147	8	309		

Based on Table 10, the obtained Chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 6.77$) with a p-value of 0.034 indicates that the association between college type and locus of control is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This

means the distribution of locus of control categories is not random and differs depending on whether students belong to a technical or non-technical institution.

Table 11

Table Showing the Association between Gender and Locus of Control

	Level of locus of control			Row Total	Chi-square value (X^2)	p
	High	Average	Low			
Male	75	74	6	155	2.107	0.349
Female	79	73	2	154		
Column Total	154	147	8	309		

Table 11 shows that the Chi-square value is 2.107, and the associated p-value is 0.349. The association between gender and the level of locus of control is not statistically significant. In other words, the distribution of locus of control categories (high, average, low) does not differ meaningfully between males and females. Any observed differences in frequency are likely due to random variation rather than a genuine gender effect.

Regression Analysis

Gender (Male-Female) and College type (Technical-Non-technical) as predictors of Locus of control among college students.

Dependent variable (DV): Locus of control

Independent Variable (IV): Gender, Type of college

Table 12

Tables Showing all the Regression Statistics for Gender + College Type \rightarrow LOC

Regression Statistics					
R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Standard Error	F	Significance F
0.147	0.022	0.015	4.51	3.391	0.035

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	p
Intercept	15.916	0.439	36.240	0.000
Gender	0.080	0.513	0.155	0.877
Type of college	1.333	0.513	2.597	0.010

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine whether gender and college type predicted locus of control. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.147$) suggests a weak positive relationship between the predictors (Gender and Type of College) and the dependent variable (Locus of Control). The model explains only 2.2% of the variance in locus of control ($R^2 = 0.022$). The Adjusted $R^2 = 0.015$ confirms that the explained variance remains very small even after adjusting for the number of predictors (Table 12). This indicates that, while the model is statistically significant, gender and college type account for only a small portion of the variation in locus of control scores.

The overall regression model is statistically significant, $F(2, 306) = 3.391$, $p = 0.035$. This means that the combination of predictors explains locus-of-control differences significantly, even though the effect size is small. The type of college was a significant predictor ($\beta = 1.333$, $p = .010$), indicating that students from different college types differed in their locus of control scores. However, gender was not a significant predictor ($\beta = 0.080$, $p = .877$), suggesting no

meaningful gender-based difference in locus of control in this sample.

Discussion

This study set out to explore whether the type of academic stream technical versus non-technical and gender are associated with differences in locus of control among college students in Bihar. Based on the results of this study, it can be inferred that the type of college has some impact on the level of locus of control. On the other hand, no significant gender differences were found. These findings carry several important implications and warrant discussion in light of existing research and the socio-educational context of Bihar.

The significant impact of college type on the level of LoC obtained in ANOVA, chi-square, and regression analyses is inconsistent with Naik's (2015) work in Gulbarga, which reported no LoC disparity between arts and science streams. Gandhi et al. (2022) also observed variations in LOC profiles among college students in different disciplines in Chandigarh. To explain this scenario, two

studies note that management and professional courses often expose students to competitive, performance-oriented environments where external constraints (placement opportunities, market conditions) are salient (Yadav et al., 2021; Sharma, 2023).

Our two-way ANOVA results for gender impact mirror Napowanetz's (2014) report that "no significant relationship between both genders regarding a more dominant locus of control orientation" was found. Verma and Shah (2017) also did not find any significant difference in LOC by gender. Yadav et al. (2021) studied LOC in male and female management students in Delhi NCR and found no significant difference in LOC orientation between both genders. The finding of no gender difference in locus of control among Bihar college students is encouraging from an equality standpoint. It suggests that female students in Bihar are just as likely as males to feel in command of their academic fate—a sign that educational empowerment is reaching both genders. Many recent studies have shown similar trends where the gap in male and female scores on psychological traits was found to be smaller in the context of the young population of India. One explanation of this change could be that education is a moderating factor and it has power to reverse traditional and societal norms that treated male and female differently in social settings. On account of this change, females are starting to feel independent and responsible for their actions. Our finding echoes this same sentiment that females are perceiving themselves in control of whatever is happening in their lives. However, the sample for this study has limited context, so it is possible that in other sections of society, a gender gap may be present.

Very few studies are available on locus of control in college settings in Bihar. One relevant study is Rani's (2024) PhD thesis. In this study she noted that locus of control is linked to better adjustment and life satisfaction. This study was conducted on university students in Bihar. In this study, differences based on the type of colleges were not studied. Still, there is one key observation for students' overall well-being in this study. If we want to enhance the feeling of satisfaction in students, then it is critical to boost their sense of personal control.

Implications for Education

The findings of this study are relevant for educators as well as institutions in Bihar. To some extent, it can be generalised to other similar contexts. This study suggested that most of the students tend to have an external locus of control, so it becomes imperative that measures should be taken to enhance internal LOC among students. These measures may include continuous counselling, mentorship, and a shift in existing pedagogy. In colleges, there should be a focus on skills workshops and a mentoring programme to boost the sense of personal confidence among students. Structured guidance and feedback from teachers are also helpful for making students more engaged with the study process. This study found no significant difference in LOC based on gender. This suggests that interventions to boost internal LOC can be gender neutral. Auliya et al. (2023) also advocated that institutions should play an active role in shaping the internal locus of control. In most cases, internal LOC seems to benefit students. But some students with internal LOC may feel overburdened and can suffer from performance pressure. This may result in stress and anxiety. In such a scenario, it becomes essential that there should be a balance between fostering motivation and managing expectations.

Many studies have shown that male students display more internal LOC in general and female students display more external LOC. But this should not be overgeneralised. One should understand that there are many exceptions and complexities rooted in different academic and social contexts. So, the interventions to boost internal LOC should be rooted in a specific context. Taking the differences in LOC of technical and non-technical students is crucial to adopt better-suited interventions. Fostering an internal LOC through programs targeted to specific students will help boost students' motivation and performance in study (Watkins, 1987; Mayora-Pernía & Fernández de Morgado, 2015). Curriculum should be designed in a way that emphasises personal responsibilities and the value of effort, so students may strive for better academic outcomes (Watkins, 1987; Akin, 2010).

Limitations of the Study

- The sample is limited to selected institutions in Bihar, so the study's results may not be generalisable to all contexts.
- The study design was cross-sectional; longitudinal designs could be used to examine the process of acquiring LOC.
- All measures were based on self-report, so there is room for self-report bias that can adversely impact the findings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study presents differences in LOC among technical and non-technical college students in Bihar. It was found that, in general, technical college students tend to have an external locus of control. This difference was very subtle. Gender was not found to be statistically significant in this context. So, it seems that academic streams are a more differentiating factor than gender. While adopting strategies to improve the education level, one should be sensitive to cultural and social factors. Socio-economic disparities and gender differences should also be addressed while trying to boost internal LOC among students. This research is based on a limited sample from Bihar, so its results should be generalised with caution. This study opens avenues for further research in this context.

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Received October 14, 2025

Revision received October 26, 2025

Accepted October 30, 2025